

POLYGONAL NUMBERS: NEW PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

The investigators were able to come up with this study because of the inspiration from the different sequences learned from grade 10 and in the Pre-Calculus subject in this school year. They were motivated to make another type of sequence and they thought of creating a sequence from polygons. The investigation used an inductive theory development that involved searching for patterns from observations and developing formulas of the n th term from those patterns. It was found out that there were sequences formed and from those patterns, the researchers were able to form and validate three formulas. The formulas where s represents the number of matchsticks used as a perimeter of the first polygon formed and n is the number of terms are: first is $(s-2)n^2 = a_n$, for the number of equilateral triangles formed; second is $\frac{3(s-2)n^2 + sn}{2} = a_n$, for the number of matches used is:, and third is $\frac{(s-2)n^2 + sn + 2}{2} = a_n$, for the number of intersections of the matchsticks found in a polygon, which were confirmed applicable in finding the n th term of any polygon formed by m number of matchsticks.

Keywords: *Sequences, Polygons, Patterns, Formulas, Equilateral triangles, Matchsticks, Perimeter, Intersection*

INTRODUCTION

In number theory, there are different kinds of sequences and one of these is a number sequence. According to Eather (2014), a number sequence is an ordered set of numbers arranged according to a rule. In the history of Mathematics, many sequences were discovered such as; arithmetic sequences, geometric sequences, Fibonacci sequences, and harmonic sequences. Because of these discoveries, the researchers were inspired to make another type of sequence and they thought of creating a sequence from polygons.

Polygonal numbers are numbers representing dots that are arranged into a geometric figure. Starting from a common point and augmenting outwards, the number of dots utilized increases in successive polygons, (Betancourt and Park, 2009).

According to Betancourt and Park (2009), the idea of polygonal numbers was first discovered by the Greek mathematician Hypsicles in the year 170 BC. Hypsicles as the author of the polygonal numbers concluded that the n th n -gon can be calculated using the formula $\frac{n[2 + (n-1)(n-2)]}{2}$. He used this formula to determine the number of elements

in the n th term of a polygon with a side. Before Hypsicles, there are evidences that Greek mathematicians used such figurate numbers to create their theories. One polygonal of these was found by Pythagoras, Pythagorean's theorem, where he discovered that the area of the square built upon the hypotenuse of a right triangle is equal to the sum of the areas of the squares upon the remaining sides (Morris, 2019) establishing a formula $a^2 + b^2 = c^2$ where a , b and c are measurements of the two adjacent sides and the hypotenuse respectively (Chipalata, 2004), which is commonly used in the study of geometry today.

Some mathematical formulations have deep roots in polygonal numbers and several famous theorems are based on these numbers such as Mersenne prime, Fermat numbers, Fibonacci sequence, Lucas numbers, Pascal's triangle, and binomial theorem, and others which are applied in our modern mathematics.

According to Hosch (2019), in number theory, Mersenne prime is a prime number of the form $2^n - 1$ where n is a natural number where these primes are a subset of the Mersenne numbers, M_n . The numbers are named for the French theologian and mathematician Marin Mersenne, who asserted in the preface of *Cogitata Physica-Mathematica* (1644) that, for $n \leq 257$, M_n is a prime number only for 2, 3, 5, 7, 13, 17, 19, 31, 67, 127, and 257. The list contained two numbers that produce composite numbers and omitted two numbers that produce primes. The corrected list is 2, 3, 5, 7, 13, 17, 19, 31, 61, 89, 107, and 127, which was not determined until 1947. This shadowed the work of various mathematicians through the centuries, starting with the Swiss mathematician Leonhard Euler, who first verified in 1750 that 31 produces a Mersenne prime.

The researchers will be investigating a new polygonal number sequence using matchsticks, forming polygons, and connecting the intersections using more matchsticks. The researchers hypothesize that they can form three sequences that have not yet been investigated. For them, it needs an investigation because despite of many investigations and results on various kinds of polygonal number sequences, there are no results that can be found for these number sequences.

Objectives of the Study

The researchers aimed to achieve the following objectives;

1. Investigate and form a polygonal sequence using matchsticks focusing on;
 - 1.1 number of equilateral triangles inside the polygon,
 - 1.2 number of matchsticks used, and
 - 1.3 number of intersections of the matchsticks
2. Create a formula for the n th term of sequences formed.

METHODOLOGY

Materials:

- Matchsticks
- Illustration board
- Glue
- Paper and pencil
- Calculator

General Procedure:

The investigators will be using an inductive theory development which involves searching for patterns from observations and development of formulas of the n th term for those patterns. First, using matchsticks the investigators will form different polygons (from 3-sided to 5-sided) with one matchstick as the length of its side and connect the intersections of matchsticks using another matchstick to form equilateral triangles and will observe how many matchsticks will be used, how many equilateral triangles will be formed and how many points of intersections (dots) will be determined. Second, using other matchsticks the investigators will form the same shapes of polygons but this time the sides will be added with one matchstick then the same process will be done. The procedure will be repeated until the investigators can form a polygon with 5 matchsticks as the length. From the recorded data the investigators will have three patterns and from those patterns, three theories for finding the n th term can be formed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Derivation for the formula on the number of equilateral triangles formed inside a polygon

A. Polygon with perimeter of $3m$ where m is a positive integer

Figure 1. Polygon with perimeter = $3m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

Using the sequence formed with the number of triangles in a polygon with perimeter = $3m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, the researchers constructed a sequential formula. The result is as follows:

Table 1. Polygonal Sequence formed from the number of equilateral triangles in a Polygon with a Perimeter of $3m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5
No. of equilateral triangles	1	4	9	16	25

1st difference: $4-1 = 3, 9-4 = 5, 16-9 = 7, 25-16 = 9$

2nd difference: $5-3 = 2, 7-5 = 2, 9-7 = 2$

As we can see in the sequence, the second difference is a constant of 2. Therefore, the researchers came up with using a quadratic sequence in the form $an^2 + bn + c$. The quadratic sequence is a sequence of numbers in which the second difference between any two consecutive terms is constant. Through this form, we substituted the value of n where n represents the term in the sequence, and equate each term with the equivalent number of triangles. We use the values of $n = 1, 2,$ and 3 .

$$an^2 + bn + c = a_n$$

$$a(1)^2 + b(1) + c = 1$$

$$a(2)^2 + b(2) + c = 4$$

$$a(3)^2 + b(3) + c = 9$$

$$a + b + c = 1 \quad \longrightarrow \text{eq. 1}$$

$$4a + 2b + c = 4 \quad \longrightarrow \text{eq. 2}$$

$$9a + 3b + c = 9 \quad \longrightarrow \text{eq. 3}$$

Finding the values of a, b, c , using the system of linear equations in 3 unknowns, the researchers came up with

$n^2 = a_n \longrightarrow$ **Formula for the number of equilateral triangles formed inside a polygon with perimeter of $3m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$**

B. Polygon with perimeter of $4m$ where m is a positive integer

Figure 2. Polygon with perimeter = $4m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

Using the sequence formed with the number of triangles in a polygon with perimeter = $4m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, the researchers constructed a sequential formula. The result is as follows:

Table 2. Polygonal Sequence formed from the number of equilateral triangles in a Polygon with Perimeter of $4m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

	a ₁	a ₂	a ₃	a ₄	a ₅
No. of equilateral triangles	2	8	18	32	50

1st difference: $8-2 = 6, 18-8 = 10, 32-18 = 14, 50-32 = 18$
 2nd difference: $10-6 = 4, 14-10 = 4, 18-14 = 4$

The second difference is a constant of 4 which is twice of the second difference found in the first table and again using the quadratic sequence in the form of $an^2 + bn + c$ with $n = 1, 2,$ and $3,$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
 an^2 + bn + c = a_n & & & \\
 a(1)^2 + b(1) + c = 2 & a + b + c = 2 & \longrightarrow & \text{eq. 1} \\
 a(2)^2 + b(2) + c = 8 & 4a + 2b + c = 8 & \longrightarrow & \text{eq. 2} \\
 a(3)^2 + b(3) + c = 18 & 9a + 3b + c = 18 & \longrightarrow & \text{eq. 3}
 \end{array}$$

Solving the values of $a, b, c,$ using the system of linear equations in 3 unknowns, the researchers came up with

$2n^2 = a_n \longrightarrow$ **Formula for the number of equilateral triangles formed inside a polygon with perimeter of $4m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$.**

C. Polygon with perimeter of $5m$ where m is a positive integer

Using the sequence formed with the number of triangles in a polygon with perimeter = $5m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, the researchers constructed a sequential formula.

Figure 3. Polygon with perimeter = $5m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

The result is reflected in the table below.

Table 3. Polygonal Sequence formed from the number of equilateral triangles in a Polygon with Perimeter of $5m, m \in Z^+$

	a ₁	a ₂	a ₃	a ₄	a ₅
No. of equilateral triangles	3	12	27	48	75

1st difference: $12-3 = 9, 27-12 = 15, 48-27 = 21, 75-48 = 27$

2nd difference: $15-9 = 6, 21-15 = 6, 27-21 = 6$

With the constant difference of 6 which is thrice of the second difference found in the first table, still using the quadratic sequence in a form of $an^2 + bn + c$ with $n = 1, 2,$ and 3.

$$an^2 + bn + c = a_n$$

$$a(1)^2 + b(1) + c = 3$$

$$a(2)^2 + b(2) + c = 12$$

$$a(3)^2 + b(3) + c = 27$$

$$a + b + c = 3 \quad \longrightarrow \quad \text{eq. 1}$$

$$4a + 2b + c = 12 \quad \longrightarrow \quad \text{eq. 2}$$

$$9a + 3b + c = 27 \quad \longrightarrow \quad \text{eq. 3}$$

Computing the values of a, b, c , using the system of linear equations in 3 unknowns, the researchers came up with

$3n^2 = a_n \longrightarrow$ Formula for the number of equilateral triangles formed inside a polygon with perimeter of $5m, m \in Z^+$

Summary of formulas (number of equilateral triangles formed inside the polygon):

$$P = 3m, m \in Z^+ = n^2$$

$$P = 4m, m \in Z^+ = 2n^2$$

$$P = 5m, m \in Z^+ = 3n^2$$

By observing these three formulas the researchers formed a general formula for the number of equilateral triangles formed inside the polygon which is equal to $(s-2)n^2 = a_n$, where s is the number of matchsticks used as a perimeter of first polygon formed and n is the number of terms.

Verification:

Validating the formula if it is applicable for a polygon with perimeter of $6m, m \in Z^+$ for term 1: $s = 6$ and $n = 1$

$$(s-2)n^2 = a_n$$

$$(6-2)(1)^2 = a_1$$

$$4(1) = a_1$$

$$4 = a_1$$

Figure 4. Polygon with perimeter = 6 by 1 matchsticks

It means there are 4 equilateral triangles formed inside a polygon with perimeter of 6 by 1 matchsticks.

For term 2:

$$s = 6 \text{ and } n = 2$$

$$(s-2)n^2 = a_n$$

$$(6-2)(2)^2 = a_2$$

$$4(4) = a_2$$

$$16 = a_2$$

Figure 5. Polygon with perimeter = 6 by 2 matchsticks

This means there are 16 equilateral triangles formed inside a polygon with perimeter of 6 by 2 matchsticks.

For term 3:

$$s = 6 \text{ and } n = 3$$

$$(s-2)n^2 = a_n$$

$$(6-2)(3)^2 = a_3$$

$$4(9) = a_3$$

$$36 = a_3$$

Figure 6. Polygon with perimeter = 6 by 3 matchsticks

It means that there are 36 equilateral triangles formed inside a polygon with a perimeter of 6 by 3 matchsticks.

Since it is verified that the formula is true for a polygon with a perimeter of $6m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, thus, the researchers' formula for the nth term of the sequence formed from the number of equilateral triangles formed inside the polygon is true for all polygons with perimeter of n matchsticks.

Derivation for the formula on the number of matchsticks used

A. Polygon with perimeter of $3m$ where m is a positive integer

Figure 7. Polygon with perimeter = $3m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

Using the sequence formed with the number of matchsticks in a polygon with perimeter = $3m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, the researchers constructed a sequential formula. The result is as follows:

Table 4. Polygonal Sequence formed from the number of matchsticks used in a Polygon with a Perimeter of $3m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5
No. of matchsticks used	3	9	18	30	45

1st difference: $9-3 = 6$, $18-9 = 9$, $30-18 = 12$, $45-30 = 15$

2nd difference: $9-6 = 3$, $12-9 = 3$, $15-12 = 3$

The second difference is a constant of 3 and still using the quadratic sequence in the form of $an^2 + bn + c$ with $n = 1, 2$, and 3 .

$$an^2 + bn + c = a_n$$

$$a(1)^2 + b(1) + c = 3$$

$$a(2)^2 + b(2) + c = 9$$

$$a(3)^2 + b(3) + c = 18$$

$$a + b + c = 3$$

$$4a + 2b + c = 9$$

$$9a + 3b + c = 18$$

————→ eq. 1

————→ eq. 2

————→ eq. 3

Finding the values of a, b, c , using the system of linear equations in 3 unknowns, the researchers came up with

$3/2n^2 + 3/2n = a_n$ ——— **Formula for the number of matchsticks used on a polygon with perimeter of $3m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$**

B. Polygon with perimeter of $4m$ where m is a positive integer

Figure 8. Polygon with perimeter = $4m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

Using the sequence formed with the number of matchsticks in a polygon with perimeter = $4m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, the researchers constructed a sequential formula. The result is presented in the table:

Table 5. Polygonal Sequence formed from the number of matchsticks used in a Polygon with a Perimeter of $4m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5
No. of matchsticks used	5	16	33	56	85

1st difference: $16-5 = 11, 33-16 = 17, 56-33 = 23, 85-56 = 29$

2nd difference: $17-11 = 6, 23-17 = 6, 29-23 = 6$

The second difference is a constant of 6 which is twice of the second difference found in Table 4 and again using the quadratic sequence in the form of $an^2 + bn + c$ with $n = 1, 2,$ and 3 .

$$an^2 + bn + c = a_n$$

$$a(1)^2 + b(1) + c = 5$$

$$a(2)^2 + b(2) + c = 16$$

$$a(3)^2 + b(3) + c = 33$$

$$a + b + c = 5$$

$$4a + 2b + c = 16$$

$$9a + 3b + c = 33$$

—————→ eq. 1

—————→ eq. 2

—————→ eq. 3

Solving the values of a, b, c , using the system of linear equations in 3 unknowns, the researchers came up with

$3n^2 + 2n = a_n$ —————→ Formula for the number of matchsticks used on a polygon with perimeter of $4m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

C. Polygon with perimeter of $5m$ where m is a positive integer

Using the sequence formed with the number of matchsticks in a polygon with perimeter = $5m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, the researchers constructed a sequential formula.

Figure 9. Polygon with perimeter = $5m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

The result is as follows:

Table 6. Polygonal Sequence formed from the number of matchsticks used in a Polygon with Perimeter of $5m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5
No. of matchsticks used	7	23	48	82	125

1st difference: $23-7 = 16$, $48-23 = 25$, $82-48 = 34$, $125-82 = 43$

2nd difference: $25-16 = 9$, $34-25 = 9$, $43-34 = 9$

With the constant difference of 9 which is thrice of the second difference found in table 4, still using the quadratic sequence in a form of $an^2 + bn + c$ with $n = 1, 2,$ and 3 .

$$an^2 + bn + c = a_n$$

$$a(1)^2 + b(1) + c = 7$$

$$a(2)^2 + b(2) + c = 23$$

$$a(3)^2 + b(3) + c = 48$$

$$a + b + c = 7 \quad \longrightarrow \quad \text{eq. 1}$$

$$4a + 2b + c = 23 \quad \longrightarrow \quad \text{eq. 2}$$

$$9a + 3b + c = 48 \quad \longrightarrow \quad \text{eq. 3}$$

Solving the values of a, b, c , using the system of linear equations in 3 unknowns, the researchers came up with

$9/2n^2 + 5/2n = a_n \longrightarrow$ Formula for the number of matchsticks used on a polygon with perimeter of $5m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

Summary of formulas (number of matchsticks used):

$$P = 3m, m \in Z^+ = \frac{3}{2}n^2 + \frac{3}{2}n = a_n$$

$$P = 4m, m \in Z^+ = 3n^2 + 2n = a_n \text{ or } \frac{6}{2}n^2 + \frac{4}{2}n = a_n$$

$$P = 5m, m \in Z^+ = \frac{9}{2}n^2 + \frac{5}{2}n = a_n$$

By observing these three formulas the researchers formed a general formula that is equal to $\frac{3(s-2)n^2 + sn}{2} = a_n$, where s is the number of matchsticks used as a perimeter of the first polygon formed and n is the number of terms.

Verification:

Validating the formula if it is applicable for a polygon with a perimeter of $6m, m \in Z^+$ for term 1:

$$s = 6 \text{ and } n = 1$$

$$\frac{3(s-2)n^2 + sn}{2} = a_n$$

$$\frac{3(6-2)(1)^2 + 6(1)}{2} = a_1$$

$$\frac{3(4)(1) + 6}{2} = a_1$$

$$\frac{12 + 6}{2} = a_1$$

$$\frac{18}{2} = a_1$$

$$9 = a_1$$

Figure 10. Polygon with perimeter = 6 by 1 matchsticks

This means that there are 9 matchsticks being used in forming a polygon with perimeter of 6 by 1 matchsticks.

For term 2:

$$s = 6 \text{ and } n = 2$$

$$\frac{3(s-2)n^2 + sn}{2} = a_n$$

$$\frac{3(6-2)(2)^2 + 6(2)}{2} = a_2$$

$$\frac{3(4)(4) + 12}{2} = a_2$$

$$\frac{48 + 12}{2} = a_2$$

$$\frac{60}{2} = a_2$$

$$30 = a_2$$

Figure 11. Polygon with perimeter = 6 by 2 matchsticks

It means to say that there are 30 matchsticks being used in forming a polygon with perimeter of 6 by 2 matchsticks.

For term 3:

$$s = 6 \text{ and } n = 3$$

$$\frac{3(s-2)n^2 + sn}{2} = a_n$$

$$\frac{3(6-2)(3)^2 + 6(3)}{2} = a_3$$

$$\frac{3(4)(9) + 18}{2} = a_3$$

$$\frac{108 + 18}{2} = a_3$$

$$\frac{126}{2} = a_3$$

$$63 = a_3$$

Figure 12. Polygon with perimeter = 6 by 3 matchsticks

It means that there are 63 matchsticks being used in forming a polygon with perimeter of 6 by 3 matchsticks.

Since it is verified that the formula is true for a polygon with perimeter of $6m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, thus, the researchers' formula for the n th term of the sequence formed from the number of matchsticks used is true for all polygons with perimeter of n matchsticks.

Derivation for the formula on the number of intersections of the matchsticks

A. Polygon with perimeter of $3m$ where m is a positive integer

Figure 13. Polygon with perimeter = $3m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

Using the sequence formed with the number of intersections of the matchsticks in a polygon with perimeter = $3m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, the researchers constructed a sequential formula. The result is as follows:

Table 7. Polygonal Sequence formed from the number of intersections of the matchsticks used in a Polygon with Perimeter of $3m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5
No. of intersections of matchsticks	3	6	10	15	21

1st difference: $6-3 = 3$, $10-6 = 4$, $15-10 = 5$, $21-15 = 6$

2nd difference: $4-3 = 1$, $5-4 = 1$, $6-5 = 1$

The second difference is a constant of 1 and still using the quadratic sequence in a form of $an^2 + bn + c$ with $n = 1, 2, 3$.

$$an^2 + bn + c = a_n$$

$$a(1)^2 + b(1) + c = 3$$

$$a(2)^2 + b(2) + c = 6$$

$$a(3)^2 + b(3) + c = 10$$

$$a + b + c = 3 \quad \longrightarrow \text{eq. 1}$$

$$4a + 2b + c = 6 \quad \longrightarrow \text{eq. 2}$$

$$9a + 3b + c = 10 \quad \longrightarrow \text{eq. 3}$$

Solving the values of a, b, c , using the system of linear equations in 3 unknowns, the researchers came up with

$$\frac{n^2 + 3n + 2}{2} = a_n \quad \longrightarrow \quad \text{Formula for the number of intersections of matchsticks}$$

used on a polygon with perimeter of $3m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

B. Polygon with perimeter of $4m$ where m is a positive integer

Figure 14. Polygon with perimeter = $4m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

Using the sequence formed with the number of intersections in a polygon with perimeter = $4m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, the researchers constructed a sequential formula.

The result is reflected on the table.

Table 8. Polygonal Sequence formed from the number of intersections of the matchsticks used in a Polygon with Perimeter of $4m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5
No. of intersections of matchsticks	4	9	16	25	36

1st difference: $9-4 = 5, 16-9 = 7, 25-16 = 9, 36-25 = 11$

2nd difference: $7-5 = 2, 9-7 = 2, 11-9 = 2$

With the constant difference of 2 which is twice of the second difference found in the seventh table, still using the quadratic sequence in a form of $an^2 + bn + c$ with $n = 1, 2,$ and 3 .

$$an^2 + bn + c = a_n$$

$$a(1)^2 + b(1) + c = 4$$

$$a(2)^2 + b(2) + c = 9$$

$$a(3)^2 + b(3) + c = 16$$

$$a + b + c = 4 \quad \longrightarrow \text{eq. 1}$$

$$4a + 2b + c = 9 \quad \longrightarrow \text{eq. 2}$$

$$9a + 3b + c = 16 \quad \longrightarrow \text{eq. 3}$$

Solving the values of a, b, c , using the system of linear equations in 3 unknowns, the researchers came up with

$n^2 + 2n + 1 = a_n \longrightarrow$ **Formula for the number of intersections of matchsticks used on a polygon with perimeter of $4m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$**

C. Polygon with perimeter of $5m$ where m is a positive integer

Using the sequence formed with the number of intersections in a polygon with perimeter = $5m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, the researchers constructed a sequential formula.

Figure 15. Polygon with perimeter = $5m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

The result is presented on the table below:

Table 9. Polygonal Sequence formed from the number of intersections of the matchsticks used in a Polygon with Perimeter of $5m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5
No. of intersections of matchsticks	5	12	22	35	51

1st difference: $12-5 = 7, 22-12 = 10, 35-22 = 13, 51-35 = 16$

2nd difference: $10-7 = 3, 13-10 = 3, 16-13 = 3$

With the constant difference of 3 which is twice of the second difference found in the seventh table, still using the quadratic sequence in a form of $an^2 + bn + c$ with $n = 1, 2, 3$.

$$an^2 + bn + c = a_n$$

$$a(1)^2 + b(1) + c = 5$$

$$a(2)^2 + b(2) + c = 12$$

$$a(3)^2 + b(3) + c = 22$$

$$a + b + c = 5$$

$$4a + 2b + c = 12$$

$$9a + 3b + c = 22$$

→ eq. 1

→ eq. 2

→ eq. 3

Solving the values of a, b, c , using the system of linear equations in 3 unknowns, the researchers came up with

$$\frac{3n^2 + 5n + 2}{2} = a_n \longrightarrow \text{Formula for the number of intersections of matchsticks}$$

used on a polygon with perimeter of $5m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

Summary of formulas (number of intersections of matchsticks):

$$P = 3m, m \in Z^+ = \frac{n^2 + 3n + 2}{2} = a_n$$

$$P = 4m, m \in Z^+ = n^2 + 2n + 1 = a_n \text{ or } \frac{2n^2 + 4n + 2}{2} = a_n$$

$$P = 5m, m \in Z^+ = \frac{3n^2 + 5n + 2}{2} = a_n$$

By observing these three formulas the researchers formed a general formula which is equal to $\frac{(s-2)n^2 + sn + 2}{2} = a_n$, where S is the number of matchsticks used as a perimeter of the first polygon formed and n is the number of terms.

Verification:

Validating the formula if it is applicable for a polygon with perimeter of $5m, m \in Z^+$

For term 1:

$$s = 6 \text{ and } n = 1$$

$$\frac{(s-2)n^2 + sn + 2}{2} = a_n$$

$$\frac{(6-2)(1)^2 + 6(1) + 2}{2} = a_1$$

$$\frac{(4)(1) + 6 + 2}{2} = a_1$$

$$\frac{4 + 8}{2} = a_1$$

$$\frac{12}{2} = a_1$$

$$6 = a_1$$

Figure 16. Polygon with perimeter = 6 by 1 matchsticks

It means to say that there are 6 intersections of the matchsticks found in a polygon with perimeter of 6 by 1 matchsticks.

For term 2:

$$s = 6 \text{ and } n = 2$$

$$\frac{(s-2)n^2 + sn + 2}{2} = a_n$$

$$\frac{(6-2)(2)^2 + 6(2) + 2}{2} = a_2$$

$$\frac{(4)(4) + 12 + 2}{2} = a_2$$

$$\frac{16 + 14}{2} = a_2$$

$$\frac{30}{2} = a_2$$

$$15 = a_2$$

Figure 17. Polygon with perimeter = 6 by 2 matchsticks

This means that there are 15 intersections of the matchsticks found in a polygon with perimeter of 6 by 2 matchsticks.

For term 3:

$$s = 6 \text{ and } n = 3$$

$$\frac{(s-2)n^2 + sn + 2}{2} = a_n$$

$$\frac{(6-2)(3)^2 + 6(3) + 2}{2} = a_3$$

$$\frac{(4)(9) + 18 + 2}{2} = a_3$$

$$\frac{36 + 20}{2} = a_3$$

$$\frac{56}{2} = a_3$$

$$28 = a_3$$

Figure 18. Polygon with perimeter = 6 by 3 matchsticks

It means that there are 28 intersections of the matchsticks found in a polygon with perimeter of 6 by 3 matchsticks.

Since it is verified that the formula is true for a polygon with perimeter of $6m, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, thus, the researchers' formula for the nth term of the sequence formed from the number of intersections of the matchsticks in a polygon is true for all polygons with perimeter of n matchsticks.

Conclusions

The researchers formulated 3 general formulas for three different sequences: number of equilateral triangles formed, number of matches used, and number of intersections of the matchsticks found in a polygon which were investigated by forming polygons with equilateral triangles in them using matchsticks. The formula for the number of equilateral triangles formed is: $(s-2)n^2 = a_n$, for the number of matches used is: $\frac{3(s-2)n^2 + sn}{2} = a_n$, and for the number of intersections of the matchsticks found in a polygon is: $\frac{(s-2)n^2 + sn + 2}{2} = a_n$. These formulas are very effective since in converting huge sequence of numbers, we can make it into short and exact formulas.

Recommendations

The investigators recommend for further research to verify other processes or to investigate the in another way.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors declare that there exists no conflict of interest in conducting the study, plagiarism was avoided and results were used only for research purposes.

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